

Copernicus Global Land Operations

“Vegetation and Energy”

”CGLOPS-1”

Framework Service Contract N° 199494 (JRC)

VALIDATION REPORT

MODERATE DYNAMIC LAND COVER CHANGE MAPS

AFRICA 2015-2018

COLLECTION 100M

VERSION 2.1

Issue I1.00

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Document Release Sheet

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Approval:	Roselyne Lacaze	Sign	Date 28.10.2019
Endorsement:	Michael Cherlet	Sign	Date
Distribution:	Public		

Change Record

Issue/Rev	Date	Page(s)	Description of Change	Release
	30.08.2019	All	First issue	

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List of Acronyms

AD	Applicable documents
ATBD	Algorithm technical basis document
CEOS-WGCV	Committee on earth Observing Satellites working Group on Calibration and Validation
CGLS	Copernicus Global Land Service
CGLS_LCC100m	CGLS Moderate Dynamic Land Cover product at 100m spatial resolution
FAO	Food and agriculture organization of the united nation
FAPAR	Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LCC	Land Cover Classification
LCCS	Land Cover Classification System
LAI	Leaf Area Index
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
OECD	Economic Co-operation and Development
PSD	Product specifications document
PUM	Product user manual
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEEA	System of Environmental Economic Accounting
SSD	Service specifications document
SVP	Service validation plan
UN	United Nations
UNCCD	United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UR	User requirement
URD	User requirement document
VR	Validation report
WGS	World Geodetic System
WUR	Wageningen University and Research

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Copernicus Global Land Service (CGLS) is earmarked as a component of the Land service to operate “a multi-purpose service component” that provides a series of bio-geophysical products on the status and evolution of land surface at global scale. Production and delivery of the parameters take place in a timely manner and are complemented by the constitution of long-term time series.

Since January 2013, the Copernicus Global Land Service is continuously providing Essential Variables like the Leaf Area Index (LAI), the Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation absorbed by the vegetation (FAPAR), the surface albedo, the Land Surface Temperature, the soil moisture, the burnt areas, the areas of water bodies, and additional vegetation indices, which are generated every hour, every day or every 10 days on a reliable and automatic basis from Earth Observation satellite data.

The CGLS delivers a dynamic global land cover product at 100m spatial resolution (V2.0). The new version (i.e., CGLS_LCC100m V2.1) provides yearly moderate dynamic land cover change maps over the African continent from 2015 to 2018. The product includes discrete land cover maps and fractional cover layers for 2015-2018.

This report presents the consistency assessment and an initial indication of accuracy of the Africa yearly maps 2016-2018. The consistency assessment was performed using the validation data for 2015. As such, the results provided in this report only show how consistent are the maps with each other. Indeed, the statistical accuracy of these maps (2016-2018) can only be calculated once additional validation datasets for change areas are collected. In addition to the assessment of consistency, we report on the change area within the period of 2015-2018 together with visual estimates of land cover changes. Furthermore, an assessment of difference between the Africa 2015 V2.1 map and the existing global 2015 V2.0 product is included.

Main results of the consistency assessments show that the yearly 2015-2018 V2.1 maps are temporally consistent. Based on validation data of 2015, the accuracy of the maps stays within similar range in overall accuracy: 80.4%, 80.1%, 79.9% and 79.5% for 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018, respectively. The decreased trend in the overall accuracy could be due to using a validation dataset of 2015. Indeed, the 2015 validation dataset does not represent the changes that occurred within the temporal gap between 2015 and the mapping period.

The change area calculations showed that approximately 1 % of yearly changes occurred within this period. When checked collectively between 2015 and 2018, the overall change area was around 2.3%. Visual assessments of the land cover change areas revealed accurate detection of water expansion, deforestation and cropland expansion. However, visual verification also identified false detection of change in cropland areas, forest and wetland areas that requires improvements.

Comparative assessment of the new version (V2.1) of the CGLS_LCC100m product compared to the existing global V2.0 within Africa reveals slight improvement in overall accuracy (80.4% for

V2.1 vs. 80.1% for V2.0). Notably, confusions related to shrubs and herbaceous vegetation classes are reduced, thus resulting for higher accuracies for these classes. The version 2.1 has slightly reduced representation of shrubs compared to V2.0, what improves the correspondence with very high resolution images.

These results indicate that the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 yearly maps of Africa are temporally consistent, without much overestimation of changes, and depict correctly different land change processes with, however, some misclassifications. These achievements can be further improved by collecting reference datasets to better characterize the land cover changes and, thus, reducing the main limitation of the mapping and change detection methodology.

1 BACKGROUND OF THE DOCUMENT

1.1 SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES

This document describes the validation of the CGLS Moderate Dynamic Land Cover 100m V2.1 product (CGLS_LCC100m V2.1) which includes yearly land cover maps between 2015 and 2018 for Africa. It presents the objectives of the validation process, provides details on the method and the results of the validation.

1.2 CONTENT OF THE DOCUMENT

This document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 recalls the users requirements and the expected performance
- Chapter 3 describes the data and methodology used for the consistency assessment
- Chapter 4 presents the results of the analysis
- Chapter 5 summarizes the main conclusions of the study
- Chapter 6 makes recommendations based upon the results

1.3 RELATED DOCUMENTS

1.3.1 Applicable documents

AD1: Annex I – Technical Specifications JRC/IPR/2015/H.5/0026/OC to Contract Notice 2015/S 151-277962 of 7th August 2015

AD2: Appendix 1 – Copernicus Global land Component Product and Service Detailed Technical requirements to Technical Annex to Contract Notice 2015/S 151-277962 of 7th August 2015

AD3: GIO Copernicus Global Land – Technical User Group – Service Specification and Product Requirements Proposal – SPB-GIO-3017-TUG-SS-004 – Issue I1.0 – 26 May 2015.

1.3.2 Input

Document ID	Descriptor
CGLOPS1_SSD	Service Specifications of the Copernicus Global Land Service “Vegetation and Energy” component
CGLOPS1_SVP	Service Validation Plan of the Copernicus Global Land Service
CGLOPS1_URD_LC100m	Users Requirement Document of Moderate Dynamic Land Cover 100m product
CGLOPS1_PSD_LC100m	Product Specifications Document of the Moderate

Dynamic Land Cover product

CGLOPS1_VR_LC100m-V2.0 Validation report for global Moderate Dynamic Land Cover V2.0 product

1.3.3 Output

Document ID

Descriptor

CGLOPS1_PUM_LCC100m-V2.1

Product User Manual Moderate Dynamic Land Cover Change V2.1 product

2 REVIEW OF USERS REQUIREMENTS

According to the applicable documents [AD2] and [AD3], the user's requirements relevant for Dynamic Moderate Land Cover are:

- **Definition:** Dynamic global land cover products at 300m and/or 100m resolution using UN Land Cover Classification System (LCCS)
- **Geometric properties:**
 - Pixel size of output data shall be defined on a per-product basis so as to facilitate the multi-parameter analysis and exploitation.
 - The baseline datasets pixel size shall be provided, depending on the final product, at resolutions of 100m and/or 300m and/or 1km.
 - The target baseline location accuracy shall be 1/3 of the at-nadir instantaneous field of view.
 - Pixel co-ordinates shall be given for centre of pixel.
- **Geographical coverage:**
 - geographic projection: lat long
 - geodetical datum: World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84)
 - pixel size: 1/112° - accuracy: min 10 digits
 - global window coordinates:
 - Upper Left: 180°W-75°N
 - Bottom Right: 180°E, 56°S
- **Accuracy requirements:** Overall thematic accuracy of dynamic land cover mapping products shall be >80%. The overall accuracy assessment (including confidence limits) will be based on a stratified random sampling design and the minimum number of sampling points per land cover class relevant to the product shall be calculated as described in Wagner and Stehman, 2015.

Few workshops were held in 2016 to consult different stakeholders to understand users' needs for global land cover maps. A feasibility study was performed to define the guidelines to create the first LC100 map. More details can be found in [CGLOPS1_URD_LC100m]. Larger consultations in 2017 and 2018 allowed collecting the requirements of wide user communities which were translated in product specifications [CGLOPS1_PSD_LC100m]. Below land cover type and land change processes that were found to be important for different international actions and programmes are summarized in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Figure 1: Land change processes and land cover transformations by user requirement

Table 1: Usefulness of information on LC and LC change processes for different international actions and programmes

	LC types	Related land change processes	UNFCCC	UNCCD	OECD	SEEA/FAO	SDGs
1	Urban/built-up areas	Urbanization	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	Cropland	Crop expansion	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3	Cropland and other vegetation	Land abandonment	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4	Forest	Deforestation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
5	Forest	Reforestation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
6	Wetland	Wetland degradation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
7	Water body	Expansion of water surface			✓	✓	✓
8	Water body	Reduction of water surface			✓	✓	✓
9	Bare areas	Desertification			✓	✓	✓

3 QUALITY ASSESSMENT METHOD

The objective is to assess the temporal consistency of the yearly land cover Africa maps for 2015-2018. The consistency is assessed using the validation dataset for Africa for the year 2015. In addition, visual verifications are conducted to check the quality of land cover characterization for 2016-2018, focusing on areas that are reportedly changed according to the 2015 reference map.

3.1 OVERALL PROCEDURE

The evaluation of the consistency of the yearly land cover v2.1 maps (CGLS_LCC100m V2.1) between 2015 and 2018 for Africa is performed using a validation dataset collected for the year 2015 [CGLOPS1_VR_LC100m-V2.0]. This validation dataset was used for both the assessment of discrete land cover map and the fractional land cover layers. Since the validation dataset is available only for year 2015, we focused our assessments on the temporal consistency between the yearly land cover maps. Upon collecting additional validation sites in change areas within this period, the statistical accuracy of the yearly maps can be calculated.

In addition to the consistency assessments, we report on the change area within the period based on the maps and as well as visual evaluation of detected changes. We further elaborate on the difference between the global 2015 land cover map in CGLS_LC100m V2.0 and the Africa 2015 land cover map in CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 that is assessed in this report.

The subsections below describe the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 product that was the subject of the analysis (Section 3.2), *in situ* 2015 validation dataset (Section 3.3), the methods for map assessment (Section 3.4), land cover change assessment (Section 3.5) and visual assessment of difference between CGLS_LC100m V2.0 and CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps over Africa (Section 3.6).

3.2 CGLS_LCC100M V2.1 PRODUCT FOR AFRICA (2015-2018)

CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 provides an improved moderate land cover map of 2015 over the African continent comparing to CGLS_LC100m V1.0, and continuous maps for 2016, 2017 and 2018. The new version includes discrete land cover maps and fractional land cover layers, which are generated from the PROBA-V 100 m time-series, a database of high quality land cover training sites, and several ancillary datasets. The detailed description of the map generation is presented in the PUM [CGLOPS1_PUM_LCC100m-V2.1].

The discrete maps provide 23 classes (Table 2), following the Land Cover Classification System (LCCS) developed by the United Nations (UN) Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). The UN-LCCS system was designed as a hierarchical classification, which allows adjusting the thematic detail of the legend to the amount of information available:

- The “level 1” legend contains classes with codes that are multiples of ten in Table 2 (i.e. class values of 10, 20, 30, etc.).

- The “level 2” legend, a more detailed legend known as regional legend, has class codes of two digits that is not a multiple of ten in Table 2 (i.e. class values of 11, 12 are sub-classes of 10, and so on).
- The “level 3” legend has three digits (i.e. 111–116 and 121–126) and are used to further distinguish the forest types (sub-classes of 11– open forest and 12– closed forest).

The 2015 discrete map is considered as the base map as it is the starting point of the product. It was generated using 3-year PROBA-V remote sensing data (2014, 2015 and 2016). The maps for 2016 and 2017 are CONSO (consolidated) mode and the 2018 map is NRT (near real time) mode. CONSO mode represents maps where any possible changes would be consolidated with the use of remote sensing data of one full year after the year end. For example, for 2016 map, data for the full period of 2015, 2016 and 2017 are used. The NRT mode represents maps where any possible change are detected but not consolidated, due to no sufficient time after the year end. In NRT mode, only 3 months data after the year end is used. For example, for 2018, there is no one full year data available after the end of this year. Figure 2-Figure 5 show the discrete land cover maps at Level 3 for 2015-2018 over Africa.

Besides discrete maps, the product also include fractional land cover layers for forest, shrubland, herbaceous vegetation, cropland, urban, bare/sparse vegetation, moss/lichen, snow, permanent and seasonal water. With continuous classification scheme, they may depict areas of heterogeneous land cover better than the standard classification scheme and, as such, can be tailored for various applications (e.g. forest monitoring, biodiversity and conservation, climate modelling, etc.).

Table 2: Discrete classification coding of the CGLS dynamic land cover map V2.1

Map code	UN LCCS level	Land Cover Class	Definition according UN LCCS	Color code (RGB)
0	-	No input data available	-	0, 0, 0
111	A12A3A10B2D2E1	Closed forest, evergreen needle leaf	tree canopy >70 %, almost all needle leaf trees remain green all year. Canopy is never without green foliage.	88, 72, 31
113	A12A3A10B2D2E2	Closed forest, deciduous needle leaf	tree canopy >70 %, consists of seasonal needle leaf tree communities with an annual cycle of leaf-on and leaf-off periods	112, 102, 62
112	A12A3A10B2D1E1	Closed forest, evergreen, broad leaf	tree canopy >70 %, almost all broadleaf trees remain green year round. Canopy is never without green foliage.	0, 153, 0
114	A12A3A10B2D1E2	Closed forest, deciduous broad leaf	tree canopy >70 %, consists of seasonal broadleaf tree communities with an annual cycle of leaf-on and leaf-off periods.	0, 204, 0
115	A12A3A10	Closed forest, mixed	Closed forest, mix of types	78, 117, 31
116	A12A3A10	Closed forest, unknown	Closed forest, not matching any of the other definitions	0, 120, 0
121	A12A3A11B2D2E1	Open forest, evergreen needle leaf	top layer- trees 15-70 % and second layer- mixed of shrubs and grassland, almost all needle leaf trees remain green all year. Canopy is never without green foliage.	102, 96, 0

Map code	UN LCCS level	Land Cover Class	Definition according UN LCCS	Color code (RGB)
123	A12A3A11B2D2E2	Open forest, deciduous needle leaf	top layer- trees 15-70 % and second layer-mixed of shrubs and grassland, consists of seasonal needle leaf tree communities with an annual cycle of leaf-on and leaf-off periods	141, 116, 0
122	A12A3A11B2D1E1	Open forest, evergreen broad leaf	top layer- trees 15-70 % and second layer-mixed of shrubs and grassland, almost all broadleaf trees remain green year round. Canopy is never without green foliage.	141, 180, 0
124	A12A3A11B2D1E2	Open forest, deciduous broad leaf	top layer- trees 15-70 % and second layer-mixed of shrubs and grassland, consists of seasonal broadleaf tree communities with an annual cycle of leaf-on and leaf-off periods.	160, 220, 0
125	A12A3A12	Open forest, mixed	Open forest, mix of types	146, 153, 0
126	A12A3A12	Open forest, unknown	Open forest, not matching any of the other definitions	100, 140, 0
20	A12A4A20B3(B9)	Shrubs	These are woody perennial plants with persistent and woody stems and without any defined main stem being less than 5 m tall. The shrub foliage can be either evergreen or deciduous.	255, 187, 34
30	A12A2(A6)A20B4	Herbaceous vegetation	Plants without persistent stem or shoots above ground and lacking definite firm structure. Tree and shrub cover is less than 10 %.	255, 255, 76
90	A24A2A20	Herbaceous wetland	Lands with a permanent mixture of water and herbaceous or woody vegetation. The vegetation can be present in either salt, brackish, or fresh water.	0, 150, 160
100	A12A7	Moss and lichen	Moss and lichen	250, 230, 160
60	B16A1(A2)	Bare / sparse vegetation	Lands with exposed soil, sand, or rocks and never has more than 10 % vegetated cover during any time of the year	180, 180, 180
40	A11A3	Cultivated and managed vegetation/agriculture (cropland)	Lands covered with temporary crops followed by harvest and a bare soil period (e.g., single and multiple cropping systems). Note that perennial woody crops will be classified as the appropriate forest or shrub land cover type.	240, 150, 255
50	B15A1	Urban / built up	Land covered by buildings and other man-made structures	250, 0, 0
70	B28A2(A3)	Snow and Ice	Lands under snow or ice cover throughout the year.	240, 240, 240
80	B28A1B1	Permanent water bodies	lakes, reservoirs, and rivers. Can be either fresh or salt-water bodies.	0, 50, 200
200	B28A1B1 ¹	Open sea	Oceans, seas. Can be either fresh or salt-water bodies.	0, 0, 128

Figure 2: The CGLS Dynamic Land Cover Map at 100 m for Africa 2015 (see legend in Table 2)

Figure 3: The CGLS Dynamic Land Cover Map at 100 m for Africa 2016 (see legend in Table 2)

Figure 4: The CGLS Dynamic Land Cover Map at 100 m for Africa 2017 (see legend in Table 2)

Figure 5: The CGLS Dynamic Land Cover Map at 100 m for Africa 2018 (see legend in Table 2)

3.3 IN-SITU REFERENCE PRODUCTS

The yearly land cover maps are assessed using an independent dataset collected specifically for the validation of CGLS_LCC100m products. This reference land cover information, which also contains land cover fraction information, represents the year 2015. More detailed information on the sample selection and reference data collection processes are provided in the validation report of global V2.0 product [CGLOPS1_VR_LC100m-V2.0].

From the global validation dataset, we selected the 3616 sample sites located in Africa. Figure 6 shows the spatial distribution of these validation sample sites and the stratification used for the data collection.

Figure 6: Spatial distribution of validation sample sites and the stratification by Olofsson et al 2012: 'p' before the strata names denote populated part of climate zone.

3.4 ASSESSMENT OF TEMPORAL CONSISTENCY OF CGLS_LCC100M

The CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 product (including both the discrete maps and fractional land cover layer for 2015-2018) is assessed using the independent validation dataset described in Section 3.3. Specifically, for the discrete maps, a confusion or error matrix is calculated for each year based on the mapped and reference land cover types. The error matrix is corrected by sample inclusion probabilities (Tsendbazar et al., 2018). Detailed information on map accuracy assessment can be found in CGLOPS1_VR_LC100m-V2.0.

Note that the analysis focuses on Level 1 legends which does not account for different forest classes.

For the fractional land cover layers, the mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE) were calculated.

$$RMSE_c = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i (p_i - v_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i}} \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

$$MAE_c = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i |p_i - v_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i} \quad (\text{Eq.2})$$

where $RMSE_c$ is the root mean squared error of class c , v_i is the reference fraction of class c (in percent), p_i is the mapped fraction of class c , ω_i represents the estimation weight for the sample site and n is the total number of sample sites.

Since the validation dataset does not contain reference land cover information for 2016-2018, the error matrices and accuracies are indicators of the temporal consistency between the yearly maps rather than the statistical accuracy. For the statistical accuracy, additional sample sites in updated or changed areas are required. The overall map accuracies and specific class accuracies of different years are further compared to evaluate the temporal consistency between the yearly maps for Africa.

3.5 LAND COVER CHANGE 2015- 2018

3.5.1 Statistical analysis

We calculate the total area of each of the 9 Level 1 land cover class over 2015-2018 based on the Mollweide equal area projection at continental scale. The percentage of each class out of total area of Africa is also calculated. Based on these, we compare the change areas for each land cover class per year and over the whole period (2015-2018).

The spatial difference between two land cover maps is also calculated by directly subtracting the two maps. Pixels that have a value equal to zero in the resulting map indicate no land cover change occurred while non-zero values indicate land cover changed between two maps. The total area for those changed pixels is then summarized to reveal the overall land cover change in Africa. Since the changes between “shrubs” and “herbaceous vegetation” are not of high importance according to the users’ requirement thus these two classes are combined as “other vegetation” class (Figure 1).

3.5.2 Visual assessment

To investigate if the land cover change information is well captured by the product, we have performed visual validation by comparing the change maps with available satellite imagery from Google Earth, Sentinel imagery and Bing maps.

Based on the user requirements on land use/land cover change information (Chapter 2), several land change processes (e.g. deforestation, crop expansion, water expansion/reduction) are selected and checked based on the change areas between 2015 and 2018 detected by the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps. Figure 7 shows the spatial distribution of selected change locations across Africa.

3.6 ASSESSMENT ON DIFFERENCE BETWEEN CGLS_LC100M V2.0 AND CGLS_LCC100M V2.1 OVER AFRICA

Since CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 is produced with special focus on temporal consistency and detection of changes through 2015 and 2018 for Africa, it has some differences when comparing with the global 2015 map in CGLS_LC100m V2.0. The differences are assessed by comparing the confusion matrix provided from the result of section 3.4 and confusion matrix for Africa that is included in the CGLOPS1_VR_LC100m-V2.0 report. In addition, we highlight visual differences between the two versions.

4 RESULTS

4.1 TEMPORAL CONSISTENCY OF THE CGLS_LCC100M V2.1 PRODUCT FOR AFRICA (2015-2018)

Discrete land cover maps

The confusion matrixes of the discrete land cover maps for the year 2015-2018 are shown below in Table 3, Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 3: A confusion matrix (%) for CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 discrete land cover map at Level 1 for 2015, corrected by sample inclusion probabilities

	Forest	Shrubs	Herbaceous vegetation	Croplands	Urban	Bare/sparse vegetation	Permanent Water	Herbaceous Wetland	Correct count	Total	User's accuracy	Confidence interval \pm
Forest	25.45	1.55	0.99	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.07	25.45	29.10	87.46	2.20
Shrubs	2.96	10.41	2.23	0.98	0.00	0.36	0.01	0.12	10.41	17.07	60.98	6.10
Herbaceous vegetation	1.19	1.46	9.67	0.83	0.01	0.80	0.04	0.27	9.67	14.27	67.76	6.30
Croplands	0.69	0.76	0.98	4.69	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.15	4.69	7.30	64.25	6.80
Urban	0.15	0.00	0.09	0.01	0.28	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.54	51.85	20.50
Bare/sparse vegetation	0.02	0.22	1.25	0.00	0.01	28.48	0.00	0.00	28.48	29.98	95.00	2.90
Permanent Water	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.01	0.00	1.01	1.02	99.02	0.60
Herbaceous Wetland	0.20	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.11	0.35	0.35	0.72	48.61	19.2
Correct count	25.45	10.41	9.67	4.69	0.28	28.48	1.01	0.35				
Total	30.66	14.41	15.26	7.50	0.31	29.68	1.22	0.96		100.00		
Producer's accuracy	83.01	72.24	63.37	62.53	90.32	95.96	82.79	36.46			80.40	
Confidence interval \pm	2.60	5.80	6.50	6.70	3.90	2.50	10.30	17.40				1.90

Table 4: Same table as provided in Table 3, but here showing the results for 2016

	Forest	Shrubs	Herbaceous vegetation	Croplands	Urban	Bare/sparse vegetation	Permanent Water	Herbaceous Wetland	Correct count	Total	User's accuracy	Confidence interval \pm
Forest	25.51	1.48	1.04	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.11	25.51	29.18	87.42	2.20
Shrubs	2.99	10.25	2.14	1.05	0.00	0.36	0.01	0.16	10.25	16.96	60.44	6.20
Herbaceous vegetation	1.19	1.60	9.61	0.83	0.01	0.80	0.01	0.25	9.61	14.30	67.20	6.30
Croplands	0.68	0.81	1.00	4.59	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.11	4.59	7.23	63.49	6.80
Urban	0.15	0.00	0.09	0.01	0.28	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.54	51.85	20.50
Bare/sparse vegetation	0.02	0.22	1.23	0.00	0.01	28.47	0.01	0.00	28.47	29.96	95.03	2.90
Permanent Water	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	1.04	0.00	1.04	1.05	99.05	1.20
Herbaceous Wetland	0.19	0.00	0.13	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.11	0.32	0.32	0.78	41.03	17.90
Correct count	25.51	10.25	9.61	4.59	0.28	28.47	1.04	0.32				
Total	30.73	14.36	15.24	7.5	0.31	29.68	1.23	0.95		100.00		
Producer's accuracy	83.01	71.38	63.06	61.20	90.32	95.92	84.55	33.68			80.10	
Confidence interval \pm	2.60	5.90	6.50	6.80	3.90	2.50	9.10	16.70				1.90

Table 5: Same table as provided in Table 3, but here showing the results for 2017

	Forest	Shrubs	Herbaceous vegetation	Croplands	Urban	Bare/sparse vegetation	Permanent Water	Herbaceous Wetland	Correct count	Total	User's accuracy	Confidence interval ±
Forest	25.52	1.46	0.95	1.02	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.11	25.52	29.10	87.70	2.20
Shrubs	2.97	10.14	2.19	1.01	0.00	0.35	0.01	0.20	10.14	16.87	60.11	6.20
Herbaceous vegetation	1.14	1.67	9.52	0.78	0.01	0.80	0.01	0.30	9.52	14.23	66.90	6.30
Croplands	0.71	0.88	1.03	4.69	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.10	4.69	7.46	62.87	6.70
Urban	0.15	0.00	0.09	0.01	0.28	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.54	51.85	20.50
Bare/sparse vegetation	0.02	0.22	1.20	0.00	0.01	28.47	0.01	0.00	28.47	29.93	95.12	2.90
Permanent Water	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	1.04	0.00	1.04	1.07	97.20	2.10
Herbaceous Wetland	0.23	0.00	0.18	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.23	0.23	0.76	30.26	16.40
Correct count	25.52	10.14	9.52	4.69	0.28	28.47	1.04	0.23				
Total	30.74	14.37	15.16	7.53	0.31	29.68	1.23	0.94		100.00		
Producer's accuracy	83.02	70.56	62.80	62.28	90.32	95.92	84.55	24.47			79.90	
Confidence interval ±	2.60	5.90	6.50	6.70	3.90	2.50	9.10	14.10				1.90

Table 6: Same table as provided in Table 3, but here showing the results for 2018

	Forest	Shrubs	Herbaceous vegetation	Croplands	Urban	Bare/sparse vegetation	Permanent Water	Herbaceous Wetland	Correct count	Total	User's accuracy	Confidence interval ±
Forest	25.57	1.57	1.02	0.98	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.11	25.57	29.29	87.30	2.20
Shrubs	2.94	9.57	2.13	0.98	0.00	0.35	0.01	0.20	9.57	16.18	59.15	6.30
Herbaceous vegetation	1.14	1.89	9.51	0.78	0.01	0.80	0.01	0.30	9.51	14.44	65.86	6.50
Croplands	0.71	0.85	1.06	4.76	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.06	4.76	7.49	63.55	6.70
Urban	0.15	0.00	0.09	0.01	0.28	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.54	51.85	20.50
Bare/sparse vegetation	0.02	0.44	1.20	0.00	0.01	28.46	0.00	0.00	28.46	30.13	94.46	3.20
Permanent Water	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	1.05	0.00	1.05	1.09	96.33	2.40
Herbaceous Wetland	0.23	0.00	0.22	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.10	0.28	0.28	0.86	32.56	16.40
Correct count	25.57	9.57	9.51	4.76	0.28	28.46	1.05	0.28				
Total	30.76	14.32	15.23	7.53	0.31	29.69	1.23	0.95		100.00		
Producer's accuracy	83.13	66.83	62.44	63.21	90.32	95.86	85.37	29.47			79.50	
Confidence interval ±	2.60	6.60	6.50	6.70	3.90	2.50	9.00	15.60				2.00

Overall map accuracies are 80.4%, 80.1%, 79.9% and 79.5% for 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018, respectively, showing consistency in high overall map accuracy over time. There is a slight decrease in the map accuracy over years. This trend could be explained by the fact that the validation data covers only 2015 and temporal gap increases for the latter years. It is possible that

changes in land cover might have occurred at validation sample locations after 2015 and that information is not included in the validation data.

In terms of class specific accuracies, forest, bare/sparse vegetation, and permanent water are mapped with higher accuracy (>82%). The class accuracies of herbaceous vegetation, shrubs, and croplands are moderate (60%-70%), while urban and wetlands have lower class accuracies (<60%). This trend is observed for all the years. In addition, class specific accuracies of the consolidated maps (2016-2017) deviate maximum of 2% from 2015 class specific accuracies, except for wetland which presents larger deviation. This might due to the highly dynamic characteristics of herbaceous wetland. It may experience temporal shifts to herbaceous vegetation and permanent water. Another explanation can also be generic difficulty of mapping wetland areas. The class accuracies of the NRT map (2018) have higher deviation (~5%). This could be partially due to larger temporal gap between the reference dataset (2015) and the map (2018) and also partially due to the NRT mode in which the detected changes are not consolidated. General minimal deviation in the class accuracies indicates that there is quite high consistency between the yearly maps for Africa.

Fractional land cover maps

The CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 fractional land cover maps, namely tree cover, shrub cover, grass cover, crops, urban, bare/sparse vegetation, lichen/moss and permanent water, are assessed using the cover fraction information provided in the validation dataset. Table 7 lists the mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE) for the fractional land cover maps.

Table 7: Accuracy of the fractional land cover maps 2015-2018

		Trees	Shrub	Grass	Crops	Urban	lichen/moss	Bare/ sparse vegetation	Permanent water
2015	MAE (%)	8.2	11.6	15.7	5.6	0.7	0.0	5.0	0.4
	RMSE (%)	15.3	17.5	24.5	16.8	6.1	0.5	14.2	4.4
2016	MAE (%)	8.3	11.7	15.7	5.7	0.7	0.0	5.0	0.3
	RMSE (%)	15.4	17.6	24.3	17.4	6.1	0.5	14.4	4.3
2017	MAE (%)	8.5	11.9	15.9	5.9	0.7	0.0	5.0	0.4
	RMSE (%)	15.7	17.9	24.5	17.6	6.1	0.5	14.4	4.5
2018	MAE (%)	8.8	12.3	17.0	6.9	0.7	0.0	5.6	0.4
	RMSE (%)	16.0	18.5	25.6	18.7	6.1	0.5	14.7	4.5

Among the fractional land cover layers, rare classes such as lichen/moss, permanent water and urban area fraction maps show the lowest errors. Grass fraction maps have the highest errors for all years ($MAE \geq 15.7\%$). Similar to the overall accuracies of the discrete maps, the errors tend to increase over time. For example there is 1.3% increase in MAE for grass and crops between 2015 and 2018. This could be partially due to the temporal gaps between the map and the validation data which may have larger impact on more dynamic land cover class such as crops, and partially due to the NRT mode of 2018 map as indicated above.

4.2 LAND COVER CHANGE 2015-2018

4.2.1 Statistical analysis

Table 8 and Table 9 show the area of land cover changes depicted by the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 Africa land cover maps. From Table 8, we can see that bare area is the main land cover in 2015 with 35.21% of the total area of Africa, followed by forest area (closed forest and open forest) (28.80%), shrubs (13.30%), herbaceous vegetation (13.25%), and cropland (7.99%).

The area of forest marginally increases from 28.80% ($884.34 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$) in 2015 to 29.07% ($892.61 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$) in 2018. Cropland area also marginally increases from 7.99% ($245.23 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$) in 2015 to 8.23% ($252.72 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$) in 2018. The area of wetland has a slight increase between 2015 and 2018 ($13.15 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$ for 2015 vs $14.97 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$ for 2018). On the other hand, shrubs, herbaceous vegetation and bare area decrease from 2015 to 2018. For example, shrubs decrease from 13.30% ($406.97 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$) in 2015 to 12.84% ($405.03 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$) in 2018. Urban area and water are quite stable over time.

Table 8: Land cover area, percentage of each class, percentage of change area for Level 1 classes between 2015 and 2018

Classes	2015		2016		2017		2018		2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2015-2018
	$\times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$	%	%	%	%	%						
Forest	884.34	28.80	884.65	28.81	888.11	28.92	892.61	29.07	0.01	0.11	0.15	0.27
Shrubs	408.34	13.30	406.04	13.22	402.11	13.10	394.17	12.84	-0.08	-0.13	-0.26	-0.46
Herbaceous vegetation	406.97	13.25	407.76	13.28	405.84	13.22	405.03	13.19	0.03	-0.06	-0.03	-0.06
Cropland	245.23	7.99	246.28	8.02	249.41	8.12	252.72	8.23	0.03	0.10	0.11	0.24
Urban	7.29	0.24	7.29	0.24	7.29	0.24	7.29	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Bare/sparse vegetation	1081.27	35.21	1081.22	35.21	1079.96	35.17	1079.37	35.15	0.00	-0.04	-0.02	-0.06
Permanent water	23.91	0.78	24.10	0.78	24.13	0.79	24.34	0.79	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01
Herbaceous Wetland	13.15	0.43	13.16	0.43	13.66	0.44	14.97	0.49	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.06
lichen/Moss	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	3070.50	100.00	3070.50	100.00	3070.50	100.00	3070.50	100.00				

We also estimated the change area for Africa between 2015 and 2018 without considering the changes between “shrubs” and “herbaceous vegetation”, as these changes are not indicated as important by the users (Figure 1). Thus “shrubs” and “herbaceous vegetation” were combined as “another vegetation” class (Figure 1 and section 3.5.1) in the estimation. Table 9 shows the change area in Africa between the years and for the whole period. The land cover changes observed in the V2.1 Africa maps are maximum of 1% yearly change. For the period between 2015 and 2018, 2.29% of the area is changed.

Table 9: Land cover area change in Africa between 2015 and 2018 (the changes between “shrubs” and “herbaceous vegetation” are not included in the calculation)

	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2015-2018
Changed area ($\times 10^4$ km ²)	30.86	30.53	25.85	70.33
Total area ($\times 10^4$ km ²)	3070.50	3070.50	3070.50	3070.50
Change percentage	1.00%	0.99%	0.84%	2.29%

4.2.2 Visual assessment

Figure 7 shows the spatial distribution of selected change locations across Africa. The visual assessment results are shown in Figure 8-13.

Figure 7: The spatial distribution of selected change locations across Africa. (ESRI background layer, blue colour indicates the change areas between 2015 and 2018 detected by the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 Africa maps, red dots show the selected locations)

Example 1: Southern Ghana; Coordinates: 6.458°N, 2.029°W

Description: The CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps have detected loss of forest and expansion of flooded areas along the Ghana river over 2015-2016 (Figure 8 a, b). Google Earth imagery

confirms the deforestation and increase of regularly flooded pond areas (Figure 8 e, f). Figure 8g and Figure 8h clearly show the creation of new inundated ponds during 2015. Actually, the appearance of these man-made ponds is due to large mining activities in Ghana. The CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps capture well the process of deforestation and expansion of flooded and inundated areas.

Figure 8: An example showing the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps successfully detecting loss of forest and expansion of inundated area in Ghana. Color legend is shown in Table 2.

Example 2: Morocco; Coordinates: 30.589°N, 8.713°W

Description: The CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps have detected agriculture land expansion in an area in Morocco over 2015-2018, which is confirmed from Google Earth imagery.

Figure 9: An example showing the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps detecting the crop land expansion in Morocco. Color legend is shown in Table 2.

Example 3: Cameroon; Coordinates: 13.661°E, 5.436°N

Description: The CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps have detected a newly created reservoir in Cameroon. It was detected as “herbaceous wetland” at the beginning of the reservoir impoundment and, in the following years (2017 and 2018), as “permanent water”. The successive maps have captured the appearance and expansion of this reservoir from 2015 to 2018. This process can be further confirmed by Landsat-8 imagery.

Figure 10: An example showing the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps successfully detected a newly created reservoir in Cameroon. Color legend is shown in Table 2.

Example 4: Border of Mozambique and Malawi; Coordinates: 35.816°E, 15.642°S

Description: The area is an irregularly flooded wetland. Inside the wetland, there are shifts between “permanent water” and “herbaceous wetland” over 2015-2018. The CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps have well detected these dynamics.

Figure 11: An example showing detection of permanent water wetland dynamics by CGLS_LCC100m V2.1. Color legend is shown in Table 2.

Although some of the processes related to land cover change have been correctly captured by the yearly maps, some spurious changes are also detected in the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps. The examples are shown in Example 5-6.

Example 5: Eastern Sudan; Coordinates: 36.163°E, 16.364°N

Description: In this area, overestimation of bare/sparse vegetation has been observed. According to the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps, this bare area has changed to cropland since 2017. Sentinel-2 imagery shows increased greenness in 2017 and 2018. However, this area is covered with shrubs (based on Google Earth images) but is misclassified as cropland in the 2017 and 2018 maps.

Figure 12: An example showing false detection of cropland expansion by the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps. Color legend is shown in Table 2.

Example 6: Southwestern Angola; Coordinates: 13.751°E, 16.512°S

Description: Shrubs were misclassified as forest in the 2017 and 2018 map. The CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps have detected increased forest area. However, High resolution imagery confirms that the area is still covered by shrubs.

Figure 13: An example showing false detection of forest expansion by CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 maps. Color legend is shown in Table 2.

4.3 ASSESSMENT OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN CGLS_LC100 V2.0 AND GGLS-LC100 V2.1

CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 African yearly map (2015) assessed in section 4.1 has some differences from the CGLS_LC100m V2.0 global 2015 land cover map. We compared the confusion matrix of both maps (Table 10 for the CGLS_LC100m V2.0 and Table 3 for CGLS_LCC100m V2.1).

A slight improvement in the overall accuracy is noted for V2.1 (Overall accuracy of 80.4% for V2.1 vs. 80.1% for V2.0). In terms of different land cover classes, users and producers accuracies of shrubs increased around 3-4%. Particularly, there has been decrease in shrub to herbaceous vegetation confusions. As such there is also a slight improvement in the herbaceous vegetation producer's accuracy. The method used for V2.1 is oriented towards a temporally consistent mapping, in which some variables that tend to increase yearly variability were excluded [CGLOPS1_PUM_LCC100m-V2.1]. This seems to also have worked well for characterization of certain classes such as shrubs. However, cropland in V2.1 has slightly lower class accuracies (~2%) than V2.0. Further, producer's accuracy of the wetland class has decreased, with slight omission of this class in V2.1.

Table 10: Confusion matrix of the CGLS_LC100m V2.0 discrete map at Level 1 for Africa (from [CGLOPS1_VR_LC100m-V2.0])

Africa	Forest	Shrubs	Herbaceous vegetation	Croplands	Urban	Bare/sparse vegetation	Permanent Water	Herbaceous Wetland	Correct count	Total	User's accuracy	Confidence interval ±
Forest	25.5	1.7	1.0	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	25.5	29.2	87.5	2.2
Shrubs	3.0	9.7	2.5	0.9	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.1	9.7	16.6	58.3	6.4
Herbaceous vegetation	1.1	1.8	9.6	0.8	0.0	0.6	0.1	0.2	9.6	14.2	67.2	6.7
Croplands	0.5	0.8	1.1	4.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	4.9	7.4	66.4	6.4
Urban	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.5	52.8	20.5
Bare/sparse vegetation	0.0	0.3	1.2	0.0	0.0	28.7	0.0	0.0	28.7	30.3	94.9	2.9
Permanent Water	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	99.6	0.6
Herbaceous Wetland	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.8	48.0	18.4
Correct count	25.5	9.7	9.6	4.9	0.3	28.7	1.0	0.4				
Total	30.6	14.2	15.6	7.5	0.3	29.7	1.2	1.0		100.0		
Producer's accuracy	83.5	68.2	61.4	65.0	94.1	96.8	83.0	42.0			80.1	
Confidence interval ±	2.6	6.6	6.5	7.2	3.9	2.1	10.3	18.0				2.0

Visual assessment of the differences further confirms the results above. In general, only local scale differences between the versions are observed. Generally, decreased shrub areas are observed in the V2.1 map compared to V2.0 map. As indicated by the differences in confusion matrices, better distinction of herbaceous vegetation from shrubs is observed in V2.1 Figure 14b compared to V2.0 Figure 14a. Figure 14c shows generally similar pattern but with slight difference in open forest

areas. V2.1 depicts slightly more open forest areas which seem to correspond with the very high resolution ESRI background image.

Figure 14: Comparison between V2.0 and V2.1 in some locations in Africa (a. Northern DRC 20.482°E 4.332°N; b. Nigeria and Cameroon border 14.693°E 12.115°N; c. Southern Angola 18.765°E 16.349°S). Color legend is shown in Table 2.

Figure 15: Comparison between V2.0 and V2.1. a. Shrub areas are underestimated in the V2.1; b. Cropland was underestimated in both maps.

The reduced shrub area observed in V2.1 has also some negative impact in some regions. For example, in northern part of South Africa (Figure 15a), shrub areas are underestimated when checking against very high resolution background image, and mapped as grassland. Furthermore, both versions remain to miss out some local scale cropland areas such as in Ethiopia (Figure 15b).

5 CONCLUSIONS

This document reports the quality assessment of yearly land cover maps for Africa as part of the CGLS Moderate Dynamic Land Cover V2.1 product. The discrete land cover map and fraction layers for 2015-2018 were assessed in terms of temporal consistency, using a validation dataset containing around 3600 reference points for the year 2015. The assessment further includes visual verifications of change areas within the time period and comparison over Africa between the new version V2.1 and the existing version V2.0.

Our assessments showed that the CGLS_LC100 V2.1 discrete classes for Africa 2015-2018 are mapped with high temporal consistency. The overall accuracies of the yearly maps are around 80% (80.4%, 80.1%, 79.9% and 79.5% for 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018, respectively) when evaluated using the 2015 validation dataset. The slightly decreasing trend in the overall accuracy could be a consequence of using a validation dataset representative of year 2015. Indeed, it cannot represent the changes which occurred during the 2016-2018 period. For the consolidated maps (2016-2017), class accuracies deviated from 2015 by around 2% except for wetland class which displays higher deviation. Forest, bare/sparse vegetation, permanent water are mapped with high consistency, without deviation from 2015 in the class accuracies, while some changes in the accuracy are observed for shrubs, grassland, and cropland classes. Assessment of the fractional land cover layers shows that rare classes such as lichen/moss, permanent water and urban area have the lowest errors. Fractional grass maps have the highest errors for all years ($MAE \geq 15.7\%$).

The change area calculations showed that approximately 1% of yearly changes occurred within this period. When checked collectively between 2015 and 2018, the overall change area was 2.3%. Visual assessments of the land cover change areas revealed accurate detection of water expansion, deforestation and cropland expansion. Visual verification also identified false detection of change in cropland areas, forest and wetland areas that requires improvements.

Comparative assessment of the new version for Africa (CGLS_LCC100m V2.1) and the V2.0 within Africa revealed slight improvement in overall accuracy (80.4% for V2.1 vs. 80.1% for V2.0). Notably, confusions related to shrubs and herbaceous vegetation classes are reduced, resulting in higher accuracy for these classes. The version 2.1 had slightly reduced representation of shrubs compared to V2.0, which improved the agreement with very high resolution images.

In summary, the yearly 2015-2018 maps of CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 product are temporally consistent in mapping accuracy. As demonstrated by the visual assessment, they are capable of depicting land cover changes that have occurred during this period. However, there are also areas that are falsely detected as change. This highlights that further tuning of land cover change detection and mapping is needed for the yearly map generation, particularly for yearly mapping at global scale.

6 RECOMMENDATIONS

Analysis of the yearly land cover maps of Africa from 2015 to 2018 showed high temporal consistency in overall mapping accuracy. Despite some misclassification, the CGLS_LCC100m V2.1 can accurately detect land cover changes. Further work can focus on the improvements of the mapping and change detection methodology, and the validation procedure.

Land cover change detection and land cover characterization processes could be further fine-tuned to reduce the confusion errors and false detection of land cover changes. Collecting reference datasets of land cover change can be useful in further improvement of the land cover change detection. Special attention should be paid to land cover types that rely on auxiliary data, such as built up areas and permanent water. In the event of updated data are not available for the recent period, additional efforts should be spent to reduce the dependency on auxiliary data for an operational production of yearly land cover maps. In addition, the version 2.1 covers only Africa. For producing yearly maps for other continents, the land cover change detection algorithm set-up for Africa should be tested in areas outside this continent, given the variability of land change processes that occur across the globe.

Furthermore, the quality assessment could be improved by gathering additional validation datasets corresponding to the mapping period in order to perform statistical accuracy assessment of the yearly 2016-2018 maps in compliance with Stage 4 validation requirements of the CEOS Calibration and Validation Working Group (WGCV). Particularly, validation sample points could be collected in areas that are reported changed by the land cover maps.

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